

AI·EFFECT

Artificial Intelligence Experimentation Facility
For the Energy seCTor

D3.1 – AI Services Onboarding and AI-EFFECT Catalogue

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility
AIOD	AI On Demand
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
WP	Work Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation.
AI4EU	AI for European Union

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Executive Summary

The Work Package 3 (WP3) primarily focuses on the design of the AI-EFFECT platform and its implementation to ensure that the use cases designed in WP1 and the framework architecture developed in WP2 are properly demonstrated to the target audience. The motivation of WP3 is to standardise the AI pipeline for all the operations in the AI-EFFECT project so that the testing facilities across the nodes can be made scalable. This will also help to create the AI Catalogue for the AI vendors and users to try and build more solutions on top of the AI pipelines listed in the AI-EFFECT Project.

The WP3 will also serve as the foundation for WP4 for infrastructure deployment, validation, and testing. Task 3.1 focuses on onboarding of the components and containerization in the AI-EFFECT catalogue that involves the integration of developed nodes into a standard TEF (Testing and Experimentation Facility) platform infrastructure like AI4EU (AI 4 Europe). This report includes the process of onboarding the services defined by the nodes into the AI4EU platform to design the solutions using the Design Studio provided by the AI4EU platform.

As part of Task 3.1, each node in the AI-EFFECT Project develops a mock-up use case that includes the key actors, data providers and the overall high-level workflow. These mock-ups form the basis for onboarding models on the AI On Demand Platform, where they can be tested and validated for building AI solutions for the clients. The Task 3.1 supports all nodes in preparing the required artifacts – such as Protobuf files, Docker URIs, and model definitions which will help them in interacting with available AI models and data-transformation services to validate their respective mock-ups and build the AI Catalogue for the AI-EFFECT Project.

The onboarding process in Task 3.1 provides the foundation for orchestration mechanisms to be defined in Task 3.2 for the deployment and testing of AI service pipelines, including the certification nodes. Task 3.1 ensures the containerisation of all use cases and the required Protobuf files so that the pipelines can be managed by the orchestrator.

This document details the procedures defined in WP3 for integrating the TEF business use case from each node into standardized Design Studio Platform, the preparation of mock-ups for demonstrating the interactions, and the requirements for publishing models and services in the AI Catalogue.

1 Introduction

The objective of Task 3.1 is to design and develop the components required for the onboarding of components developed by the nodes of AI-EFFECT project through containerising the services and making them available through a Docker URI. WP3 will contribute to build the AI-EFFECT Web Portal, where all the TEF business use cases and services will be listed, and Task 3.1 is the initial step that can define the underlying working of the AI-EFFECT Web Portal. WP3 will also standardise the AI pipeline for all the operations in the AI-EFFECT Project and create the AI Catalogue, so that the testing facilities across the nodes can be made scalable. For Task 3.1, the focus will be on aggregating the mock-ups from all four nodes to deploy and test an AI model testing environment and analyse the usability and compatibility with WP4, which focuses on deployment. To accomplish this, we need to test the onboarding and containerization tasks in some of the standard frameworks available for AI projects that can connect the datasets, tools, services, etc., to design an AI solution. To make the onboarding and containerization effective and streamlined to integrate with the AI-EFFECT web portal, we are also exploring the potential of an open-source platform that supports building, composing and deploying AI pipelines so that all four nodes can utilise it for offering TEF business use cases based on their respective TEF test cases.

For this task, we have analysed potential platforms such as OpenML, Mistral.Ai, AI4Europe, and AI4Media, which also perform similar functions for testing AI models and building solutions for various business cases. The detailed analysis is included in Section 2. From the analysis, we found AI4EU Platform to be closely aligned with the AI-EFFECT Project. This also provides the Design Studio to help the nodes to design the business use cases and create and validate the solution.

Task 3.1 aims to leverage the AI4EU Platform for the AI-EFFECT Project to onboard the models developed by the four nodes. For onboarding the components, the AI4EU platform mandates a Protobuf file for each model. As part of Task 3.1, we are also building an additional wrapper class for services that are not in proto format to support the onboarding. This task forms the foundation for Task 3.2 in designing the orchestrator part for the AI-EFFECT project and also supports WP4 in deployment. Even though the current activities are mostly focusing on testing, onboarding and deployment using the AI4EU Platform, during the final phase of the project, we will be using the AI-EFFECT Web Portal to integrate the onboarding process and AI4EU testing. This can be realised only when all the nodes have listed the services and business use cases, as different services may have different levels of integration with the onboarding platform. Also, the external data interactions, simulators, and other components are integrated with the AI model for the specific services need to be tested for dependencies before containerization.

AI Catalogues to be created for the AI-EFFECT Platform are also tested and compared for standardisation with the AI4EU Platform in Task 3.1 and will be integrated with the Graphene platform upon the finalisation of the web portal of AI-EFFECT. The Graphene Platform acts as an integration and orchestration layer; enabling different AI tools, datasets, and services to communicate through standardised interfaces and APIs. Task 3.1 can be considered as the building block of the AI-EFFECT Platform that sets the path for each service and corresponding business use case to be integrated with AI models for the large-scale adoption of the AI-EFFECT Project.

2 AI Design Studio

Onboarding AI services from the nodes will be the initial element of the AI-EFFECT Platform, as shown in Figure 1. This will support the AI Catalogue and also help in testing the use cases and different business scenarios defined by the nodes. For this, we need an AI-EFFECT Web Portal that supports the onboarding module of the AI-EFFECT Central Platform. When the AI-EFFECT Web Portal is finally made live to the public with the AI services from the nodes, the portal should have an integrated design studio that helps the nodes and users to onboard and test the AI models and to design the solutions that can be executed in different environments. A GUI-based design studio can also help the users to try out various combinations of services compatible with the AI models using a drag-and-drop model, which can help to develop innovative AI solutions that can be deployed in WP4. In this section, we have analysed the potential open-source platforms that can support the AI-EFFECT Web Portal for this onboarding process.

As show in Figure 1 : AI-EFFECT Overall Concept The two layers composing the AI-EFFECT architecture can be seen: on the top, the centralised platform, containing the AI-EFFECT catalogue and the related functionalities. On the platform, data/service providers and consumers can be onboard and upload their tools or datasets, while defining the related access policies. The test scenarios can be defined with respect to the intended experiment or validation process, and the related test profile is generated to deploy the needed building blocks. The bottom layer represents the distributed testing nodes, interconnected using the VILLASframework, that allow the actual deployment of the test case and its execution. The interconnection between the two layers is managed by the VILLASframework interface and the AI-EFFECT components orchestration service.

Figure 1 : AI-EFFECT Overall Concept

2.1 AI4EU

The AI4EU (<https://www.ai4europe.eu/>) European project [1], which runs from 2019-2021 and is funded by the European Commission, was originally proposed to use Acumos AI (<https://www.acumos.org/>) as a place to experiment with AI tools from a catalogue. Replacing Acumos, the Eclipse Graphene is now used as the foundation of AI4EU, which only stores references to Docker images (Docker image URIs). Graphene requires the models to support gRPC communication according to the container specification.

The AI4EU Project is envisaged with a goal to create an On-Demand Platform (AIOD) [2] to make AI and Machine Learning algorithms accessible to a wider audience. This also aims to create an extensive marketplace for reusable solutions from a wide range of AI toolkits and languages that normal developers (not the AI experts) can utilize to create their own applications. AI4EU requires models to be packaged as Docker containers for modularity and compatibility with their pipeline-building tools.

2.2 OpenML

OpenML (<https://www.openml.org/>) is a collaborative platform for sharing datasets, algorithms, and experiments in machine learning. OpenML provides benchmarking tools, automated ML pipelines, and an open API for integration. OpenML is positioned as a worldwide machine learning lab. OpenML records exactly which datasets and library versions are used, to reduce data losses. For every experiment, the exact pipeline structure, architecture, and all hyperparameter settings are automatically stored. OpenML flows wrap around tool-specific implementations that can be serialised and later deserialised to reproduce models and verify results [3]. However, there is no visual design studio; it focuses on sharing datasets/experiments via code-based benchmarking and APIs. Better for research reproducibility than pipeline building.

2.3 Mistral AI

Mistral AI (<https://www.mistral.ai>) is a Design Studio launched in 2025 [4] that provides a Unified platform for designing, experimenting, and deploying AI workflows; reusable blocks (agents, tools, connectors, guardrails); visual experimentation environments for model variations; and governance for pipelines. At the time of writing, Mistral AI is still in the beta version and may require more time to mature as a standard design studio to test the services developed by the nodes in the AI-EFFECT Project.

2.4 AI4Media

AI4Media (<https://www.ai4media.eu/>) is funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, the project is a Centre of Excellence focused on engaging a wide network of researchers across Europe and beyond to deliver the next generation of core AI advances and training to serve the Media sector, while ensuring that the European values of ethical and trustworthy AI are embedded in future AI deployments [5].

2.5 ELIAS

ELIAS (<https://elias-ai.eu/>) stands for European Lighthouse for AI & Science for Environment [6]. ELIAS aims at establishing Europe as a leader in Artificial Intelligence (AI) research that drives sustainable innovation and economic development. ELIAS provides an AI Launchpad, which is designed for AI founders grounded in cutting-edge research and ready to scale. The idea is to unite AI hubs through one coordinated platform, giving access to local markets, networks, and support across Europe's strongest startup ecosystems.

There are many similar platforms, but most of them focus on AI algorithm development and deployment. Based on our analysis, AI4EU is the best platform for Task 3.1 because it matches the technical needs of AI-EFFECT and is already well tested in real projects. First, AI4EU uses a simple and reliable way to

onboard AI services: each service is packaged as a Docker container and communicates using gRPC, following the Eclipse Graphene specification. This makes it easy for different services, built by different nodes, to work together. Second, AI4EU provides a visual Design Studio where users can connect services, check that they work correctly, and run complete workflows without writing code. Third, AI4EU is part of the European AI-on-Demand ecosystem, which means it follows EU priorities for reusable, transparent, and standardised AI resources. For all these reasons, AI4EU fits well with the goals of Task 3.1 and gives a strong base for the orchestration and deployment work that will follow in WP3 and WP4.

3 AI Catalogue

AI Catalogue provides a detailed description of the AI assets that are published in the portal and can be downloaded and used by various users to accomplish tasks. With a wide range of similar services and functionalities, AI catalogue should possess a search facility and a standardized template for description of the service. AI4EU Platform provides an AI Catalogue which helps to search and download all the AI assets currently indexed in the AI4EU AI-on-demand platform, including AI libraries, datasets, containers, and more. While the AI Catalogue is simply a list of items that do not necessarily implement common interfaces, some of these assets have also been technically integrated into AI4EU Experiments, which can be seen as the technical part of the AI-on-demand platform. The goal is to **make AI resources discoverable, interoperable, and reusable** — especially within research, industry, and policy ecosystems.

3.1 Scope and Purpose of AI Catalogue

Understanding the fundamentals of the AI Catalogue defined for the AI4EU project [7], the AI Catalogue to be defined for the AI-EFFECT Project must include the scope and purpose for each service. This should include:

3.1.1 Target Audience

The target audience of each AI service should be clearly mentioned in the AI Catalogue. i.e., to whom the newly developed service will be helpful. It can be for researchers, government, policy makers, industry, academia, etc. This also helps to understand the level of usability of the particular service, as there can be similar AI services with similar functionalities but intended for a different target audience. In the AI-EFFECT Project, nodes can offer the same AI models to different target audiences with different set of solutions and execution environments, which can be listed in the AI catalogue.

3.1.2 Category

The category of the AI service is also needed in the AI catalogue to distinguish how the corresponding service has to be used and what dependencies and environment are required for running the service. An AI catalogue can include different categories such as AI models, datasets, algorithms, AI services, Libraries etc. The categorisation also helps in the search functionality of the catalogue to make it more efficient when there are large number of AI services being listed in the AI-EFFECT web portal.

3.1.3 Accessibility

Accessibility defines how the corresponding AI service is made available to the target audience. It should specify whether the service is private or public, or federated, so that the user can understand whether they can fully run the AI service in their own environment or have only access to run the service in the node's facility and fetch the output. Each node will have a different level of accessibility based on the services they offers and the data used for the AI model. The accessibility will also specify the usage, either as API calls, or fully downloaded, or packaged to run in an execution environment supported by

Kubernetes, etc. This provides more clarity for the users to properly run the services without any confusion. The License, version, access method, etc., will also be defined to provide transparency on the accessibility of the service.

3.2 Structure of Catalogue for AI-EFFECT

This Catalogue needs to be standardised and follow the basic definitions to provide the necessary information with transparency to the users of the AI-EFFECT Platform. As the catalogue is the first point of communication between the user and the AI-EFFECT platform to understand the services properly, it also holds a key role in the decision-making factor of the user in whether to use the service or not. A good AI service with a weak catalogue may not find the appropriate target audience, as they may lack interest with a poor definition. So it is very critical to define the structure of the AI catalogue and to follow a standard structure so that the users of the AI-EFFECT platform will have the ease to explore multiple services and use them without any confusion. If we search the AI catalogue provided by the AI4EU [7] there are still many incomplete catalogues which lack description and usage details. Analysis of user interactions on the AI Catalogue and the download patterns indicates that the majority of the solution providers and general users prefer the AI services that are well-documented and clearly structured with appropriate tags and sections in the AI Catalogue. This reflects the need for clarity on the TEF business use case and its capabilities for ensuring confidence among the users and solution providers in choosing the AI models for building solutions. Aggregating from the inputs of the AI Catalogue in the AI4EU platform, the important components to be included by the nodes while defining the service for the AI catalogue are included in the Table 1 : Structure of AI Catalogue for AI-EFFECT .

Item	Description
Model Name	Name of the AI Model
Description	A brief description of the model
Category	Dataset, Algorithm, Model, Library, etc.
Domain	Transmission, Distribution, Congestion Control, etc.
Version	Specify the version number and release date.
License	Any usage permissions and access privileges
Organisation/Owner	The node owners who list the model
Accessibility	Direct Download, API call, etc.

Table 1 : Structure of AI Catalogue for AI-EFFECT

The above Table provides the draft structure of the AI Catalogue proposed for the AI-EFFECT portal. Once we have all the TEF Business use cases being developed by all four nodes, we will reiterate on the structure to add or modify this structure based on the potential services and their business opportunity. Beyond the technical implications, the AI Catalogue should be designed with the potential users of the services and their interactions in mind. Also, there are some services where multiple nodes contribute, like the Data synthesiser, where the same service will be catering to multiple categories of audiences. The finalisation of the AI Catalogue will happen only at the time of the launch of all the business cases from the four nodes.

3.3 Policy Consideration and Validation

In addition to providing clear and complete descriptions, the AI catalogue must also meet the policy requirements of the EU, including the GDPR and ensure that legal and ethical considerations are taken care of. The AI catalogue should be a trusted source of information and requires validation of every new model getting listed. Some of the key policy suggestions and considerations for the AI catalogue of the AI-EFFECT platform are:

1. Transparency in description of models – Model descriptions must be transparent, clearly stating what the service provides, its limitations, and any conditions under which it should or should not be used
2. Who will have the authority to validate the description of the model before publishing it in the AI catalogue? There should be consortium members for validation within the AI-EFFECT Project.
3. The catalogue must respect data integrity and uphold the rights and trust of model owners, ensuring that proprietary information and datasets are handled securely and appropriately.
4. In case of duplication of models should be taken with care, understanding the differences (in any) in the usage or target audience of the service. This should not create confusion when the user is searching the model.
5. A clear conflict-resolution procedure should be established for cases where identical or overlapping models are developed jointly by multiple nodes or submitted independently in different contexts.
6. Grievance redressal and updating policy if the published services in the AI catalogue do not meet the expectations of the user, or the nodes want to revoke or update a service rather than versioning.

As mentioned earlier, these points can be considered in the validation of the AI-EFFECT infrastructure happening in WP4 and also in the governance risks discussed in WP5.

4 AI-EFFECT Platform - Onboarding Services

In this Section, the step-by-step process of onboarding the service from each node is explained. As we mentioned in the Introduction, Task 3.1 will primarily focus on onboarding the model into the AI4EU Platform to test and validate the solution, which will be later be integrated with the AI-EFFECT Platform. The overall architecture of the AI-EFFECT Platform is shown in Figure 2. The architecture comprises a Web portal, which will be live in the final phase of the AI-EFFECT project and will become the face for all the users and AI vendors to utilise the services listed by the AI-EFFECT project. The AI On-Demand platform, which connects with the Web Portal, is currently being explored in Task 3.1 for onboarding and containerising the services provided by the nodes. This will lay the foundation for the Graphene AI Framework and the AI catalogue to be built in WP3 in the upcoming tasks. The Orchestrator, which will be developed under Task 3.2, and its interaction with Task 3.1 are also shown in the architecture diagram.

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of AI-EFFECT Platform

As the node services are still under development, we planned to collect mock-ups from the nodes to understand the process and challenges in onboarding the services and also to try the design studio to create mock-up solutions that can be validated and saved to run in different environments.

For Task 3.1, the primary focus is on testing the mock-ups designed by the nodes with the Design Studio of the AI4EU (AIOD) Platform to understand the working of Eclipse Graphene [8]. As already mentioned in the introduction, Graphene does NOT build Docker images of models internally. Graphene only stores references to Docker images (Docker image URIs), never the images directly. Graphene provides the runtime and interoperability layer for the AI-EFFECT Project, where the services developed by different nodes can interact without worrying too much about the differences in interactions, programming language, ports, etc. Graphene enforces a standardised execution and communication protocol among the services being listed by the nodes in the AI-EFFECT Platform. This exercise is a preliminary requirement of Task 3.1 to ensure the mock-ups can be containerised and onboarded as Docker URIs to the AIOD platform, since the AI-EFFECT Web Portal will also utilise a similar Eclipse Graphene framework for onboarding services from the nodes of the AI-EFFECT Project.

4.1 Creating an Account in the AI4EU Platform

AI4EU is one of the promising open-source platforms provided by the EU that aligns with the business case of AI-EFFECT to test and validate the newly designed models and execute them to understand the proper working of the newly designed models. This motivated Task 3.1 to utilise the AI4EU platform and explore the functionalities of the newly built models with the help of mock-ups from each node. In order to test the compatibility of all mock-ups being developed by the nodes, a sample workshop is designed to ensure that all nodes can containerise and onboard a Docker URI to the Graphene framework in the AI4EU platform. As shown in Figure 3 each node can visit <https://www.ai4europe.eu/> to create a unique account in the AI4EU Platform to onboard and test the containerised mock-up. The user accounts are important in the AI4EU Platform to manage the permissions of models and datasets, and also for sharing the ownership and granting access rights with other participants. The user accounts support version control and reproducibility when building or deploying AI assets.

Figure 3: AI4Europe Homepage to Sign-up

Once the sign-up process is successfully completed, the nodes need to complete the e-mail verification process and then log in to the AI4EU platform on the homepage <https://aiexp.ai4europe.eu/#/home>

The screenshot displays the 'EU Login' account creation page. The page header includes 'EU Login' and 'One account, many EU services'. A language selector is set to 'English (en)'. There are links for 'Create an account' and 'Login'. The main heading is 'Create an account'. Below this, there is a form with the following fields: 'First name' (with a yellow border), 'Last name', 'email', 'Confirm email', and 'email language' (set to 'English (en)'). A checkbox is present with the text: 'By checking this box, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the [privacy statement](#)'. At the bottom of the form are 'Create an account' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 4: Account Creation Page of AI4Europe

Figure 5 : Successful completion of Account Creation

Figure 6: Confirmation Mail from AI4Europe to create the password

Figure 7: Password Creation page

Figure 8: Confirmation for successfully creating a password for the account

Figure 9: Confirmation is followed by acceptance of AIoD Terms and Conditions

Figure 10: Login Page to AI4Europe after mail verification

The homepage of the AI4EU Platform (shown in Figure 11) showcases the Design Studio and the page for onboarding the model. For onboarding a model, we need a Docker URI and Protobuf file. The relevance of Protobuf file is detailed in the coming section.

Figure 11 : Homepage of AI4EU Platform

The account creation section was included in the General Assembly workshop to ensure that each node understands the preliminary requirement for onboarding a service, designing the solution and validating with the Design Studio of AI4EU. Moreover, this also provides an overview of the Graphene framework-based Web Portal that will be finally launched for the AI-EFFECT Project, where all the nodes interact.

For the AI-EFFECT Project, this section of Task 3.1 contributed to the skeleton of designing the Web Portal, which will be the front-facing aspect of the project where all the services developed under the AI-EFFECT project will be listed by the nodes. The AI vendors and the users can use the web portal to understand the services and how they can be leveraged in their respective business domains as solutions. This will also provide a foundation for the design of the AI-EFFECT catalogue, which in turn supports WP5 in defining the business cases for long-term sustainability of the AI-EFFECT project.

4.2 Protobuf File

AI4EU mandates all projects to upload Protobuf files to onboard the services. Protocol Buffers [9], commonly termed as Protobuf, are language-neutral, platform-neutral extensible mechanisms for serializing structured data. Protocol buffers are Google’s language-neutral, platform-neutral, extensible mechanism for serializing structured data – think XML, but smaller, faster, and simpler [10]. Protobuf helps us to define how we want the data to be structured once, then we can use special generated source code to easily write and read our structured data to and from a variety of data streams and using a variety of languages. Protocol buffers support generated code in C++, C#, Dart, Go, Java, Kotlin, Objective-C, Python, and Ruby.

Protocol buffers are a combination of the definition language (created in .proto files), the code that the proto compiler generates to interface with data, language-specific runtime libraries, the serialization format for data that is written to a file (or sent across a network connection), and the serialized data. Protocol buffers provide a serialization format for packets of typed, structured data that are up to a few megabytes in size. The format is suitable for both ephemeral network traffic and long-term data storage. Protocol buffers can be extended with new information without invalidating existing data or requiring code to be updated. Figure 12 illustrates the Protobuf workflow, showing how a .proto file is compiled into source and class files for serialization and deserialization

Figure 12: Working of Protobuf (Source: <https://protobuf.dev/overview/>)

Protocol buffers are the most commonly used data format at Google. They are used extensively in inter-server communications as well as for archival storage of data on disk. Protocol buffer messages and services are described by engineer-authored .proto files. Protocol buffers are ideal for any situation in which you need to serialise structured, record-like, typed data in a language-neutral, platform-neutral, extensible manner. They are most often used for defining communications protocols (together with gRPC) and for data storage. Protobuf ensures compact data storage, fast parsing and optimised functionality through automatically-generated classes.

The first step when working with protocol buffers is to define the structure for the data you want to serialise in a *proto file*: this is an ordinary text file with a “.proto” extension. Protocol buffer data is structured as *messages*, where each message is a small logical record of information containing a series of name-value pairs called *fields*. A simple example of a calculator is shown in Figure 13, which has been used at the Aachen General Assembly workshop to provide a basic understanding for the nodes to create Protobuf file. The full source code is available at <https://github.com/IRESI-EU/AI-Effect-WP3-Aachen-Workshop>


```

syntax = "proto3";           //Defines the version of proto

service Calculator {         //Starting of service definition - Here Calculator is name of service
  rpc Add (Numbers) returns (Result); // Method definiton - Here Add is the method
}

message Numbers {          //Input message - Numbers is the input to add
  int32 a = 1;             //Field with the tag number
  int32 b = 2;
}

message Result {          //Output message
  int32 value = 1;
}

```

Figure 13: Sample Protobuf File

Then, as depicted in Figure 13, once you've specified your data structures, you use the protocol buffer compiler 'protoc' to generate data access classes in your preferred language(s) from your proto definition. These provide simple accessors for each field, as well as methods to serialise/parse the whole structure to/from raw bytes. More details to be included in the Appendix.

As per the official Google documentation, there are some challenges of Protobuf, which mentions scenarios where Protobuf cannot be used and is not a good fit. We need to consider this for the node services being developed for the AI-EFFECT Platform.

- Protocol buffers tend to assume that entire messages can be loaded into memory at once and are not larger than an object graph. For data that exceeds a few megabytes, consider a different solution; when working with larger data, you may effectively end up with several copies of the data due to serialised copies, which can cause surprising spikes in memory usage. In several common AI4EU use cases—such as long time-series, high-resolution images, or simulation outputs—payloads may exceed these practical limits, making memory spikes and performance issues a realistic concern. When handling larger data, users should employ techniques such as gRPC streaming, chunking data into smaller messages, or using alternative serialisation or file-based transfer mechanisms designed for large binary objects.
- When protocol buffers are serialised, the same data can have many different binary serialisations. You cannot compare two messages for equality without fully parsing them.
- Messages are not compressed. While messages can be zipped or gzipped like any other file, special-purpose compression algorithms like the ones used by JPEG and PNG will produce much smaller files for data of the appropriate type.
- Protocol buffer messages are not the most efficient option for scientific or engineering applications that use large multi-dimensional arrays of floating-point numbers. In these cases, formats designed for numerical data, such as FITS or similar binary scientific formats, offer much lower overhead and better performance.
- Protocol buffers are not well supported in non-object-oriented languages popular in scientific computing, such as Fortran and IDL.
- Protocol buffer messages don't inherently self-describe their data, but they have a fully reflective schema that you can use to implement self-description. That is, you cannot fully interpret one without access to its corresponding ".proto" file.
- Protocol Buffers are not an official standard from any formal standards organisation. Because of this, they may not be suitable in environments where legal, regulatory, or contractual requirements demand the use of recognised standards.

For the mock-ups being designed for the AI-EFFECT Platform, we need to consider these inputs to decide whether the service can be uploaded and tested in the AI4EU design studio and generate the solution. We

have onboarded one mock-up created by the Portuguese node for testing in AI-EFFECT platform by creating “proto” file manually for the specific mock-up on data provisioning with the knowledge store and synthetic data generation. We are also planning for a wrapper class for the mock-ups for onboarding the services by synchronising with the orchestrator service along with Task 3.2. We expect this to complete along with Task 3.2 for smoother onboarding of services.

In the meantime, we can also learn more about mock-ups from other nodes and figure out a more generic method of onboarding the services. Still, when comparing with the available services, having a Protobuf file is ideal if the service supports Protobuf format, as the goal of the platform is to provide interoperability. As the Eclipse Graphene considers all the AI services built by the nodes as a black-box running inside the Docker Container, the Protobuf file describes the gRPC communication among the services. This is detailed in Section 4.4.

4.3 Dockerisation

A container is a standard unit of software that packages up code and all its dependencies so the application runs quickly and reliably from one computing environment to another [11]. A Docker container image is a lightweight, standalone, executable package of software that includes everything needed to run an application: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries and settings.

Container images become containers at runtime and in the case of Docker containers – images become containers when they run on Docker Engine. Available for both Linux and Windows-based applications, containerized software will always run the same, regardless of the infrastructure. Containers isolate software from its environment and ensure that it works uniformly despite differences for instance between development and staging.

Containerization packages the AI services from the nodes and all its dependencies (libraries, frameworks, configurations) into a **Docker container image** — an isolated, portable runtime unit.

When the AI-EFFECT platform pulls and runs that image, it gets:

- The *same environment* you used to train and test it
- No version conflicts or dependency mismatches
- Predictable behaviour, regardless of the underlying infrastructure

AI-EFFECT Platform can integrate AI services built by **many different developers**, often in **different languages** (Python, Java, C++, R, etc.).

Containerization helps AI-EFFECT platform to avoid dependency conflicts as each service have it own isolated run-time environment. It ensures security and sandboxing as containers can isolate executions safely. Containers will also ensure scalability via orchestration and support reproducibility by the environment defined in the Dockerfile.

For WP3, we have tested the containerization using the AI4EU platform, which will be the base of the final AI-EFFECT web portal also. As per the AI4EU platform, Once the node service is containerized, the resulting **Docker image** must be stored in a container registry to be make more accessible to every user. This can be stored in Docker Hub which uniquely identified the container image.

When we onboard a service from the node, AI4EU platform uses your **Docker URI** to:

1. **Pull** the container image from the registry when needed.
2. **Deploy** it automatically in a sandboxed execution environment.
3. **Run** it without requiring your source code or manual setup.

This means the platform never depends on local files or developer environments — it simply knows *where to fetch the packaged service* and *how to run it*.

In Task 3.1, we build and push the Docker image of the mock-up from the node detailing the respective service. This is done by first pushing into the registry and obtaining the Docker URI, and using this URI in the AI4EU Platform. This contains the model logic of the service and a gRPC server. As mentioned earlier, the Protobuf file will define the communication schema for the service being onboarded.

The Eclipse Graphene runtime can pull the image using the Docker URI and launch as a container in its respective infrastructure. This also makes the gRPC communication according to the definitions in the proto file.

Containerization guarantees that any AI service behaves consistently and securely, while the **Docker URI** tells AI4EU where to fetch and how to execute that service. Together, they make AI4EU's onboarding process scalable, reliable, and interoperable.

4.4 gRPC

gRPC is a modern open source high-performance Remote Procedure Call (RPC) framework that can run in any environment [12]. It can efficiently connect services in and across data centres with pluggable support for load balancing, tracing, health checking and authentication. It is also applicable in the last mile of distributed computing to connect devices, mobile applications and browsers to backend services. By default, gRPC uses Protobuf for serialising structured data. gRPC can use protocol buffers as both its Interface Definition Language (IDL) and as its underlying message interchange format.

For the AI-EFFECT Project, the Eclipse Graphene framework defines a standard AI microservice interface for the nodes based on gRPC. When the Protobuf file is provided by a specific node, Graphene interprets it to understand the methods and message types exposed by the respective service. Parallely, the Docker URI provided by the node will be run in the Design Studio Environment by Graphene. For defining the AI pipeline for the services offered by the nodes by connecting different AI models, gRPC auto-generates the client stubs for the connections.

For defining the AI pipelines for the AI-EFFECT Platform, gRPC offers some key benefits, such as language neutrality, as all corresponding coding languages are generated by the Protobuf file. In gRPC, a client application can directly call a method on a server application on a different machine as if it were a local object, making it easier for you to create distributed applications and services. As in many RPC systems, gRPC is based around the idea of defining a service, specifying the methods that can be called remotely with their parameters and return types. On the server side, the server implements this interface and runs a gRPC server to handle client calls. On the client side, the client has a stub (referred to as just a client in some languages) that provides the same methods as the server.

4.5 Design Studio

For designing the Web Portal of AI-EFFECT Platform and to test and validate the mock-ups created by the nodes, Task 3.1 leverages the Design Studio by the AI4EU Platform as shown in Figure 11.

The **AI4EU Design Studio** is part of the **AI4EU / AI4Europe ecosystem** funded by the European Commission.

It is a **visual, low-code platform** that allows users to:

- **Compose AI workflows** by connecting reusable AI services (data preparation, model inference, analytics, etc.).
- **Onboard new AI components** (models, tools, datasets, etc.) from developers or research partners.
- **Execute** those workflows on managed infrastructures (via the **Eclipse Graphene** runtime).

In **AI4EU Design Studio**, *onboarding* a service means **registering an AI component** (model, tool, or algorithm) so it becomes part of the platform's **AI ecosystem**.

Once onboarded, other users can discover, connect, and use your component in **visual workflows** without needing to understand its internal code.

To achieve this, the platform must know two things:

1. **How to run it** → via the **Docker image / container**
2. **How to talk to it** → via the **gRPC interface defined in the .proto file**

Containerization is the key mechanism for the *first* part.

Users of AI4EU Design Studio

- See your service as a reusable component in the catalogue.
- Can drag it into workflows (e.g., “Image Preprocessing → MyModel → Visualisation”).

When executed, AI4EU automatically runs the corresponding containers behind the scenes

The detailed description of onboarding the model is included in Section 5, which was offered as a technical workshop at the General Assembly in Aachen.

5 Working Sample - Deliverable of Task 3.1

For Task 3.1, we planned to include a working sample to help all four nodes of the AI-EFFECT Project understand the potential of the AI Design Studio currently available with the AI4EU Platform. This is vital for nodes to understand all the steps in developing the AI solution by connecting the AI model with datasets, services, etc., and finally supporting deployment in the client environment. As the Design Studio follows some standard procedures for onboarding the model, we expect this working sample to help the nodes in a smoother onboarding process.

This section describes a representative working sample developed to validate the onboarding process defined in Task 3.1. The purpose of including a working sample is not to provide a detailed step-by-step guide, but rather to demonstrate how the methodology, artefacts, and tools described earlier in this deliverable operate together within the AI4EU platform. By doing so, the section illustrates how Task 3.1 contributes to the broader WP3 objective of establishing a standardised and scalable approach for integrating AI components into the AI-EFFECT ecosystem.

The working sample showcases the end-to-end flow—from preparing a mock-up use case, to registering its components in the AI Catalogue, and finally validating the workflow in the AI4EU Design Studio. Each subsection highlights the purpose of the actions undertaken and how they relate to platform interoperability, catalogue consistency, and the development of reusable AI pipelines.

5.1 Onboarding a Mock-up to the Design Studio

This subsection outlines how a mock-up use case was prepared and onboarded. The mock-up serves as a minimal yet complete example that tests the readiness of the catalogue structure, containerisation approach, and communication interfaces defined in Task 3.1. Rather than focusing on operational instructions, the description emphasises the rationale for each element:

- Protobuf definitions ensure a standardised communication interface for all services, supporting the interoperability objectives of WP3.
- Containerised components (Docker images) represent the consistent deployment format required for orchestration mechanisms in Task 3.2.
- Registration in the AI4EU catalogue validates the use of the platform as the central environment for publishing and managing AI services across the AI-EFFECT nodes.
- Design Studio integration demonstrates how nodes can compose, visualise, and evaluate workflows, reinforcing the usability and reproducibility goals of the project.

As part of the General Assembly Meeting in Aachen, WP3 conducted a workshop on Task 3.1 to support nodes in coming up with a mock-up and try the containerisation and onboarding process in the AI4EU Design Studio. The complete code repo of the workshop is available at <https://github.com/IRESI-EU/AI-Effect-WP3-Aachen-Workshop/tree/main>

Figure 14: Files under the git repo for the workshop

5.1.1 Creating the .proto file

This workshop utilises the example of a simple calculator app by creating the Protobuf file for the addition operation, and helps the nodes to familiarise how the service can be onboarded and tested in the design studio.

```

1  syntax = "proto3";           //Defines the version of proto
2
3  service Calculator {         //Starting of service definition - Here Calculator is name of service
4    rpc Add (Numbers) returns (Result); // Method definiton - Here Add is the method
5  }
6
7  message Numbers {           //Input message - Numbers is the input to add
8    int32 a = 1;              //Field with the tag number
9    int32 b = 2;
10 }
11
12 message Result {            //Output message
13   int32 value = 1;
14 }

```

Figure 15: Protobuf file created for calculator with Addition operation.

5.1.2 Testing the Communication with a client and a server

A Client and a Server code are also included which will be used for testing the working of calculator.


```

import grpc
import calculator_pb2
import calculator_pb2_grpc

channel = grpc.insecure_channel('localhost:50051')           # Connect to server
stub = calculator_pb2_grpc.CalculatorStub(channel)

result = stub.Add(calculator_pb2.Numbers(a=10, b=20))
print(f"10 + 20 = {result.value}")

```

Figure 16: Code for the client

```

1  import grpc
2  from concurrent import futures
3  import calculator_pb2           # import the generated data classes for protobuf
4  import calculator_pb2_grpc     # import the generated classes for grpc
5
6  class Calculator(calculator_pb2_grpc.CalculatorServicer):
7      def Add(self, request, context):           # implement the Add method defined in the proto file
8          result = request.a + request.b       # perform the addition
9          print(f"Calculating: {request.a} + {request.b} = {result}")
10         return calculator_pb2.Result(value=result)           # return Result message with the computed val
11
12     server = grpc.server(futures.ThreadPoolExecutor())           # create a gRPC server
13     calculator_pb2_grpc.add_CalculatorServicer_to_server(Calculator(), server) # Register our service implementation
14     server.add_insecure_port('[::]:50051')           # listen on port 50051
15     print("Server started on port 50051")
16     server.start()           # Start server (runs forever)
17     server.wait_for_termination()

```

Figure 17: Code for the server

5.1.3 Dockerfile

We will also create a dockerfile to include all the dependencies. grpcio is installed to serve the gRPC functions and Protobuf is installed to execute the .proto file

```

1  FROM python:3.9-slim           # Use an official Python runtime as a parent image
2  WORKDIR /app                  # Set working directory inside container
3  COPY . .                       # Copy all files from current directory to /app
4  RUN pip install grpcio protobuf # Install Python dependencies
5  CMD ["python", "server.py"]    # Command to run when container starts

```

Figure 18: Dockerfile

From the project structure we can see that we possess a proto file and dockerfile while we haven't written any language specific program code for the service, except for the client and server file that is provided for testing later.

5.1.4 Compiling the .proto file

Now we can use the Protobuf compiler to generate the corresponding Python file for the service and also for the gRPC server, so that we can run and test the client and server files. Here we are generating the


```

1  # Generated by the gRPC Python protocol compiler plugin. DO NOT EDIT!
2  """Client and server classes corresponding to protobuf-defined services."""
3  import grpc
4  import warnings
5  import calculator_pb2 as calculator__pb2
6  GRPC_GENERATED_VERSION = '1.73.1'
7  GRPC_VERSION = grpc.__version__
8  _version_not_supported = False
9
10 try:
11     from grpc.utilities import first_version_is_lower
12     _version_not_supported = first_version_is_lower(GRPC_VERSION, GRPC_GENERATED_VERSION)
13 except ImportError:
14     _version_not_supported = True
15
16 if _version_not_supported:
17     raise RuntimeError(
18         f'The grpc package installed is at version {GRPC_VERSION},'
19         + f' but the generated code in calculator_pb2_grpc.py depends on'
20         + f' grpcio>={GRPC_GENERATED_VERSION}.'
21         + f' Please upgrade your grpc module to grpcio>={GRPC_GENERATED_VERSION}.'
22         + f' or downgrade your generated code using grpcio-tools<={GRPC_VERSION}.'
23     )
24
25 class CalculatorStub(object):
26     """Missing associated documentation comment in .proto file."""
27
28     def __init__(self, channel):
29         """Constructor.
30
31         Args:
32             channel: A grpc.Channel.
33         """
34         self.Add = channel.unary_unary(
35             '/Calculator/Add',
36             request_serializer=calculator__pb2.Numbers.SerializeToString,
37             response_deserializer=calculator__pb2.Result.FromString,

```

Figure 20: calculator_pb2_grpc.py generated by the Protobuf compiler for gRPC communication from the proto file

The above two files are not mandatory for the design studio, as we upload only the proto file and the Docker URI. We have included the proto compiler command to help the nodes understand the usage of the proto file and how it can generate the respective code in the desired programming language to test the services locally in any environment.

5.1.5 Docker URI

Now we will build the Docker image and run the container. For that, we have to ensure that the Docker engine is up and running.

Syntax:

- docker build -t my-calculator .
- docker run -p 50051:50051 my-calculator


```
[+] Building 45.2s (10/10) FINISHED
=> [internal] load build definition from Dockerfile
=> => transferring dockerfile: 131B
=> [internal] load .dockerignore
=> => transferring context: 2B
=> [internal] load metadata for docker.io/library/python:3.9-slim
=> [1/5] FROM docker.io/library/python:3.9-slim
=> [2/5] WORKDIR /app
=> [3/5] COPY requirements.txt .
=> [4/5] RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
=> [5/5] COPY . .
=> exporting to image
=> => exporting layers
=> => writing image sha256:a1b2c3d4e5f6...
=> => naming to docker.io/library/my-calculator
```

Figure 21: Docker image being created upon running the command

Once the image is created, we will push the Docker image into Docker Hub to generate the Docker URI Syntax:

- **docker tag my-calculator YOUR_USERNAME/ai4eu-calculator**
- **docker push YOUR_USERNAME/ai4eu-calculator**

```
The push refers to repository [docker.io/yourusername/ai4eu-calculator]
a1b2c3d4e5f6: Pushed
latest: digest: sha256:1a2b3c4d5e6f... size: 1234
```

Figure 22: Creation of Docker URI

Once the Docker URI is ready, the node can login to the AI4EU (<https://aiexp.ai4europe.eu/>) to onboard the Protobuf file and the Docker URI.

5.1.6 Onboard The Dockerized Model URI

Figure 23: AI4EU On-boarding model platform

Select On-boarding Model Tab:

- Enter Model Name
- Enter Docker URI: docker.io/yourusername/ai4eu-calculator
- Browse the Protobuf file and Click upload (here it is calculator.proto)

Click **On-board Model** after the upload of calculator.proto file is complete

Figure 24: AI4EU Model Validation

We will see all three circles (Create solution, Add artifacts, and View model) in GREEN colour if the model is successfully onboarded. The View Model button will also be enabled so that we can click and see the model.

Figure 25: View Model Tab showing the model description

The model description shows the details of the model being onboarded. We can also add the License Profile for the model. The Signature will include the respective Protobuf while we uploaded, which helps to verify whether the model is offering the exact service as proposed by the node in the Protobuf file

Figure 26: Signature of Model

Figure 27: Model Artifacts

The Model Artifacts tab will showcase the log and files of the respective models with the version number and size. Once we click the Manage My Model tab, we can add the required details for publishing the model.

Figure 28: Preparing model for publishing.

Once all the required information, including Model name, description, license profile, category, documents, tags and images are uploaded, the model can be submitted for approval to be published in the catalogue.

Figure 29: Submitting model for approval to publish in AI Catalogue.

Figure 30: AI Catalogue view of the model submitted.

5.1.7 Design Studio of AI4EU

In the Design Studio, we can view the recently onboarded model in the Others tab.

Figure 31: Onboarded model in the Design Studio

Figure 32: Onboarded model in the Design Studio

From Matching Models you can find the available models to suit the end-points of your model and design the solution. Once the solution is prepared, we can click **Save** to save the solution in a respective name and version

Figure 33: Model Validation

Once the solution is saved, we can click the Validate button to ensure that all the connections between the models in the respective solution is working properly. With the onboarded model, we can create as many solutions as wanted relating to the business case and save the solutions for deployment.

Figure 34: Deploy for Execution

The Design Studio provides multiple Deployment options for executing the solutions created using the model. More detailed description on deployments will be focused in the Task 3.2 along with the Orchestrator as the scope of Task 3.1 is primarily focusing on containerising and onboarding the models created by the nodes and to utilize the Design Studio to build business solutions and validate it.

5.2 Onboarding Mock-up of Portuguese Node

In discussions with all four nodes to create a mock-up to test the containerization and onboarding of a service from the nodes, the Portuguese Node have shared a mock-up service which was onboarded to the AI4EU Design Studio for testing. The mock-up includes a data provisioning service, a knowledge store and a synthetic data generation service.

Name	Status	Date modified	Type	Size
.git	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	File folder	
data_provision	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	File folder	
docs	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	File folder	
knowledge_store	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	File folder	
synthetic_data_generation	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	File folder	
.gitignore	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	Git Ignore Source ...	1 KB
00 upload repo to OneDrive	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	Windows PowerSh...	1 KB
README	✓	10/10/2025 10:31	Markdown Source ...	1 KB

Figure 35: Mock-up services of the Portuguese node

5.2.1 Creating Solution in Design Studio

As the mock-up was not prepared with the Protobuf files, we had to prepare the Protobuf files for onboarding the mock-ups to the Design studio. In the future, we are exploring the possibilities of a wrapper class that converts mock-up services into Protobuf files when nodes are unable to provide them. In ideal scenario, we expect all nodes to provide the Protobuf file for onboarding and testing the services.

Figure 36: All 3 models from the Portuguese node onboarded successfully to the Design Studio

6 Conclusion

Task 3.1, designed to onboard the components and containerisation, has been successfully completed and demonstrated with a mock-up from the Portuguese node and through the technical workshop at RWTH-Aachen, Germany, for all the nodes to understand the activity, which will become part of the AI-EFFECT Web Portal. Once all the mock-ups from the nodes are ready to get onboarded, this document can be used as the guideline to onboard models, design, validate, and save services for the various business cases. As set in the motivation, Task 3.1 provides the foundation for standardisation of the AI pipeline for the AI-EFFECT project by accomplishing the onboarding and containerization tasks to create the AI Catalogue. In the upcoming tasks under WP3, we will leverage this potential to test the data pipeline and orchestration for the use cases, as well as for monitoring and evaluation of the scalability performances in the testing environment.

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